

First Policy Brief

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LibCommon Project Summary

LibCommon aims to stimulate innovative learning and teaching practices in HE by creating new partnerships with libraries as a commons-based resource and learning hub. This partnership between formal and non-formal education can greatly contribute to students acquiring essential competencies for today's complex society such as civic engagement, participatory citizenship, intercultural and intergenerational skills, openness to lifelong learning, critical thinking and digital competences.

Co-creating a new theoretical framework for innovation in HE in collaboration with libraries; trips to get to know in depth and learn from inspiring libraries that function as a common; blended courses to promote innovative practices in HE; and train-the-trainer activities. All of them involve students, teachers, librarians, and the community in the creation and management of new educational programmes through diverse and relevant workshops, digital courses and skill-sharing events. The main outcomes of LibCommon will be theoretical approaches; familiarisation, sharing and learning trips; policy recommendations; and training resources to support innovative HE practices in partnership with libraries. And a new model of libraries as commons and learning environments that effectively enhance lifelong learning, civic engagement and active citizenship.

Participant organisation name	Short name	Country
<u>University of Thessaly- Coordinator</u>	UTH	Greece
<u>University of Vic</u>	UVIC	Spain
<u>University of Lille</u>	ULille	France
<u>Regional Centre for Information and Scientific Development</u>	RCISD	Hungary

Executive Summary

The problem Libraries and universities have the potential to act as commons-based civic spaces, but their impact is limited without stable resources, digital inclusion, and stronger integration into policy frameworks. Inequalities persist when access, participation, and collaboration mechanisms are weak or fragmented.

Key findings confirm that Commons-based models work best with secure funding, skilled staff, and alignment with national and EU policies; those digital gaps risk reinforcing existing inequalities, making inclusion essential and that participatory governance and cross-sector collaboration improve relevance and sustainability of services.

Recommendations

- Embed commons-based approaches into national and EU strategies across education, culture, and lifelong learning.
- Formalise participatory governance and partnerships with communities to ensure meaningful engagement.
- Provide sustainable funding, professional development, and protection of libraries and universities as safe civic spaces.

1. Background and Introduction

The LibCommon project investigates how universities and libraries can function as innovative, commons-based environments for learning, civic engagement, and democratic participation. The project draws upon theories of educational commons, democratic education, and participatory governance to explore how knowledge institutions, particularly libraries and universities, can operate as shared, collectively governed resources. These institutions have the potential not only to democratise access to knowledge, but also to nurture active citizenship, community engagement, and social inclusion, especially among young people. Special attention is given to the role of youth in democratic processes, the function of libraries as social infrastructure, and the possibilities for synergies between formal and non-formal education.

The project runs for 36 months and will prepare two policy briefs: the first one -present document- is based on the initial findings of the partners, while the second one will incorporate the project results as well.

The present document is based on the activities of the first few months of the project implementation and particularly on two main activities/tasks: the literature review of

LibCommon topic on the one hand and the comparative analysis of the state of the library system in the partner countries on the other. While the first result is published as Deliverable 2.1 *Overview of the relevant Literature*, the second is D2.2 *Comparative background analysis*. Both documents are publicly available on the project website and Zenodo, and can be accessed for free.

Together, these initial outputs provide a solid evidence base for understanding the current landscape, identifying gaps, and outlining opportunities for policy action. They set the stage for the project's next phases, where deeper engagement with stakeholders and familiarization trips will further inform actionable recommendations for embedding the commons approach into European policy frameworks.

A **valuable policy framework for LibCommon's approach** is provided by the Council of Europe Recommendation CM/Rec(2023)3 on library legislation and policy in Europe (2023). This recommendation emphasises the role of libraries as public institutions of cultural, educational, and social significance, and explicitly highlights their contribution to democratic participation, social inclusion, and lifelong learning. It also aligns libraries with the United Nations 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, underlining their responsibility to foster resilience, safeguard freedom of expression, and address digital transformation challenges. Connecting LibCommon's commons-based model to this European policy reference, the project's recommendations gain additional legitimacy and demonstrate clear continuity with wider European policy efforts.

The LibCommon policy recommendations are closely **aligned with European and international policy frameworks**, which reinforces their legitimacy and relevance. In addition to the Council of Europe's Recommendation CM/Rec(2023)3 on library legislation and policy, the project supports the objectives of the European Education Area, particularly its emphasis on lifelong learning, inclusion, and cross-border cooperation in higher education (European Commission, 2020). The recommendations also resonate with the Digital Education Action Plan 2021–2027, which highlights the need for accessible, inclusive, and high-quality digital learning environments, a key component of commons-based libraries and universities (European Commission, 2020). Finally, the LibCommon approach contributes to the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, especially SDG 4 (Quality Education) and SDG 16 (Peace, Justice and Strong Institutions), by promoting equitable access to knowledge, participatory governance, and democratic civic spaces (UN, 2015). Positioning LibCommon within this wider policy ecosystem strengthens its impact potential and facilitates future uptake at both national and EU levels.

2. Key Findings

The Literature Analysis (D.2.1) have explored **how libraries, universities, and other educational institutions are increasingly conceptualised as educational commons**: shared, participatory spaces that foster learning, civic engagement, and democratic renewal. However, the transition to a commons-based educational paradigm is neither linear nor without tension.

Challenges identified:

- ⇒ **Rigid education structures**: Formal systems often prioritise hierarchy and efficiency over experimentation and co-created learning, limiting the adoption of commons-based approaches.
- ⇒ **Resource and governance barriers**: Financial constraints, bureaucratic inertia, and insufficient institutional support slow progress toward truly participatory civic hubs.
- ⇒ **Tokenistic participation**: Adoption of commons language without real power-sharing can lead to symbolic rather than meaningful involvement of youth and communities.
- ⇒ **Institutional and cultural change**: Libraries and universities require sustained institutional backing and a shift in mindset to operate as participatory, democratically governed spaces.
- ⇒ **Bridging formal and non-formal learning**: Commons-oriented libraries can connect these spheres through co-creation, participatory practices, and community-rooted initiatives.
- ⇒ **Enhanced learning experiences**: Flexible, inclusive spaces enable participatory innovative teaching, project-based learning, and community-driven research, fostering critical thinking and collaboration.
- ⇒ **Beyond digital inclusion**: Policies must address social and cultural dimensions of access to ensure responsiveness to diverse community needs.
- ⇒ **Youth activation**: Meaningful opportunities for young people to shape learning environments are essential for strengthening democratic culture.
- ⇒ **Changes in social dynamics towards individualisation and privatisation** can be subjective barriers to transforming libraries into commons
- ⇒ **The emergence of far-right populist parties that challenge the concept of knowledge and culture as a common good**, as exemplified in libraries.

The Background Analysis (D2.2) focused on three core dimensions: (1) the cataloguing of library services and their alignment with educational and social priorities, (2) the role of libraries in bridging digital divides and promoting inclusive digital practices, and (3) the strategic integration of teaching and learning approaches to empower communities. It is based on a review of reports, documentation, a series of interviews with librarians or people associated with policymaking and interviews with international experts and practitioners to contrast.

The interviews were conducted in **April 2025 across Greece, Spain, and France**, primarily via online video calls with leading professionals in the library field.

In Greece, discussions took place with figures such as Dr. Anthi Katsirikou, President of the Association of Greek Librarians and Information Scientists, Dr. Giannis Tsakonas, Director of the University of Patras Library and Vice President of LIBER, Damiana Koutsomicha, Head of the Dimitris & Aliko Perrotis Library, and Giannis Farsaris, founder of the Digital Open Library. In Spain, experts from the Municipal Library Network of the Province of Barcelona, the University of Vic, and local libraries in Vic were interviewed, including Marta Cano, General Manager of the Barcelona County Libraries network, Ignasi Janer, Director of the Pilarín Bayés Library, and social educators Núria Pérez and Txell Solà, complemented by insights from international experts such as Dr. Nicolás Barbieri and Dr. Natalia Duque Cardona.

In France, the interviews featured distinguished professionals like Julien Roche, Director of the ULille Research Library and President of LIBER, Laure Delrue, Co-director of the ULille Research Library, Julien Maréchal, Director of the Petite Bibliothèque Ronde, Hélène Brochard, Director of the Villeneuve d'Ascq Library, and Malick Diallo, Director of the Rennes Métropole Area Library and Vice-director of the French National Librarian Association.

Furthermore, partners organised a workshop on *Developing Effective Policy Briefs* during the first project meeting in Thessaloniki in June 2025 to analyse and complement these findings. (see photo)

Challenges identified:

- ⇒ **Underfunding and infrastructure gaps:** Limited budgets, inadequate digital infrastructure, and insufficient professional development restrict libraries' capacity to modernise, especially in underserved areas.
- ⇒ **Lack of national policy alignment:** Absence of coordinated strategies in Greece, fragmented local leadership in France, and reliance on political support in Spain create inconsistent access and hinder commons-based transformation.
- ⇒ **Staffing shortages and role strain:** Declining numbers of librarians, growing responsibilities, and limited recognition of their educational mission lead to staff burnout and reduced innovation capacity.

- ⇒ **Political and social pressures:** Attacks from reactionary groups, erosion of trust, and individualism weaken libraries' role as safe, inclusive civic spaces.
- ⇒ **Barriers to collaboration and shared governance:** Limited cross-sector partnerships, weak inter-library cooperation, and obstacles to participatory decision-making slow progress toward commons-based models.
- ⇒ **Unequal access across regions:** Geographic disparities persist, especially in rural or underserved communities, reinforcing the need for targeted inclusion strategies.
- ⇒ **Unequal access by social axes:** Social disparities related to class, gender, race, or disabilities reinforce the need for both universal and targeted strategies for inclusion and mixing

Therefore, the analyses call for authentic, power-aware forms of engagement, grounded in trust, shared responsibility, and sustained commitment, to avoid tokenism and cultivate meaningful, commons-based educational innovation.

3. Policy Implications

The findings indicate that:

Commons-based models work best where there is stable funding, skilled staff, and integration into policy frameworks.

Digital inclusion is essential: without it, digital infrastructure gaps reproduce inequalities.

Participatory governance improves service relevance, but requires formal support mechanisms.

Cross-sector collaboration (education, culture, social services) is vital for sustainable impact.

4. Recommendations

- 1. Establish national and EU-level strategies for commons-based libraries and universities**
Integrate the commons approach into higher education, cultural, and lifelong learning policies, ensuring alignment across ministries and with EU frameworks.
- 2. Strengthen participatory governance and community partnerships**
Formalise mechanisms for co-decision-making with students, youth, teachers, librarians, and community members to ensure meaningful participation and avoid tokenism.
- 3. Promote integration of formal and non-formal learning**
Encourage collaboration between universities, public libraries, schools, and community organisations to create shared, flexible and open learning environments.
- 4. Advance social and cultural inclusion beyond digital access**
Both redesign the existing services and initiate new programmes responsive to the lived experiences of diverse communities, oriented to address and overcome social, cultural, linguistic, geographic, and other barriers.
- 5. Invest in professional development and capacity building**
Support continuous training for librarians, educators, and community facilitators in participatory governance, digital inclusion, and commons-based pedagogies.
- 6. Secure sustainable funding and resources**
Provide multi-annual budgets for infrastructure, staffing, and innovation in both physical and digital spaces, prioritising underserved and rural areas.
- 7. Protect libraries and universities as safe civic spaces**
Safeguard their role in promoting democratic values, diversity, and intercultural dialogue against political or ideological pressures. Places where mixing and social capital can be developed.

5. References

D2.1 Overview of the relevant Literature DOI 10.5281/zenodo.15638374, LibCommon, 2025
https://rcisd.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/07/Overview-of-the-relevant-literature_Libcommon.pdf

D2.2. Comparative background analysis DOI 10.5281/zenodo.15638375, LibCommon, 2025
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